

JOURNAL OF SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH

Department of Pure and Applied Chemistry
Faculty of Physical Sciences
University of Maiduguri

Research Article

doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12100347

ON ORDER SELECTION AND FORECASTING OF GARCH MODELS FOR NON-STATIONARY AND NON-NORMAL DATA STRUCTURE

Hamid A. Chamalwa^{1*}, Harun R. Bakari² and I. Akeyede³

^{1,2}Department of Statistics, Faculty of Physical Sciences, University of Maiduguri, Borno State, Nigeria.

³Department of Statistics, Federal University Lafia, Lafia Nigeria

Corresponding Author's E-mail Address: chamalwa@unimaid.edu.ng

ABSTRACT

The study aimed to identify the orders of GARCH Models in Non-Stationarity and Non-normal data structure. Data were simulated that satisfied the non-stationary and non-normal requirement. The study fitted several GARCH models with the orders (1,1), (1,2), (2,1) and (2,2) on the simulated data at sample sizes 20, 40, 60, 80, 100, 120, 140, 160, 180 and 200 respectively. The penalty functions of AIC, BIC, SIC and HQIC used in assessing the best fit model. It was observed that parsimonious models were selected as the best fit in most of the scenario. GARCH model order selection is insensitive to the distribution which the time series conforms. Models fitted and selected for different conditions of non-Stationarity and non-normal data structure were tested on real life data with similar conditions and the selection proved to be appropriate in identifying the orders in relation to the conditions of the series. The study recommends that for every time series model order selection tests for normality and otherwise should be of priority just as that of Stationarity.

Keywords: Forecasting; GARCH model; Non-Stationary Data; Non-Normal Data Structure

INTRODUCTION

Auto-Regressive Conditional Heteroskedastic (ARCH) model was first proposed by [1] as a basic tool in stochastic variance modelling. The model drives its root from the assumption switch of the error terms of constant (homoscedastic) $\text{var}(\varepsilon_t) = \sigma^2$ to random sequence (heteroscedasticity) and its past values $(\{\varepsilon_1, \dots, \varepsilon_{t-1}\})$. It implies that, this representation has relaxed the restriction from its defunct state

This breakthrough was explained by Baillie and [2]. As it captures the volatility features of the data more appropriately. If ε_t is a white noise random variable with a mean and condition variance on I_{t-1} . then, the model for ε_t will have the following representation [3]

Therefore, an ARCH(q) model:

$$\sigma^2_t = \alpha_0 + \theta_1 \varepsilon^2_{t-1} + \dots + \theta_q \varepsilon^2_{t-q} = \theta_0 + \sum_{i=1}^q \theta_i \varepsilon^2_{t-i} \tag{1}$$

for $\theta_0 > 0$, and $\theta_i \geq 0, i > 0$. To assure $\{\sigma^2_t\}$ is a stationary random sequence of asymptotical variables, and that $\theta_1 + \theta_2 + \dots + \theta_q < 1$.

Because of some drawbacks and limitation on ARCH model, it has been extended by the so-called generalized ARCH (GARCH) model that [4] and [5] proposed independently of each other. GARCH model is a modified ARCH by simply adding σ^2_{t-j} as a lag as presented below:

$$\sigma^2_t = \theta_0 + \sum_{i=1}^q \alpha_i \varepsilon^2_{t-i} + \sum_{j=1}^p \beta_j \sigma^2_{t-j} \tag{2}$$

When, σ^2_t is replaced by h_t , we have

$$h_t = \theta_0 + \sum_{i=1}^q \theta_i \varepsilon^2_{t-i} + \sum_{j=1}^p \beta_j h_{t-j} \tag{3}$$

$$h_t = \theta_0 + \theta_1 \varepsilon^2_{t-1} + \dots + \theta_q \varepsilon^2_{t-q} + \beta_1 h_{t-1} + \dots + \beta_p h_{t-p} \tag{4}$$

where h_t is the conditional variance

$h_{t,j}$ is the past conditional variance

ε^2_{t-1} previous residual of return squared.

$\theta_0 > 0, \theta_i \geq 0, \beta_j \geq 0$.

Identification is the most crucial of the tripartite Box-Jenkins techniques, for the other two stages of estimation and diagnostic/forecasting will rely on it. An identification is an attempt to give a description of the stochastic features of the underlying time series. Hypotheses testing regarding the generating mechanism, prediction of future values and related inquiries so that the general linear model assumption is achieved [6]. Fitting a model entails getting a possible best estimate for the parameters of the given which are unknown.

The study is interested in assessing the performance of GARCH models order identification under the weak stationary condition discussed by [7] and data structure being normal and non-normal; for the non-normality exponential distribution was used. Although, there exist more than one method for selecting GARCH models, we primarily focus on the penalty functions of Akaike, Bayesian, Schwartz and Hannan-Quinn Information Criterion method facilitated by hypothetically assuming the innovation distribution to be normal, which is unarguably the most frequently used techniques in practice [8].

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The Model Considered for Simulation

The data for the study was generated from autoregressive model which is linear of order 2 as given below

$$\text{AR (2): } Y_{ti} = 0.7X_{ti-1} + 0.9X_{ti-2} + w_t, \tag{5}$$

$t = 1, 2, \dots, 20, 40, 60, 80, 100, 120, 140, 160, 180$ and $200. i = 1, 2, \dots, 1000$

The codes below was used to simulate data at the sample sizes 20, 40,.....using (5)

```
x <- w <- rnorm(200, 35, 3)
```

for $(t \text{ in } 3:50)x[t] <- 0.7*x[t-1]+0.9*x[t-2]+w[t]$

and for moving average

$$Y_{ti} \sim N(0,1) \text{ and } e_{ti} \sim N(0,1) \tag{6}$$

The above (6) will render the data simulated to be stationary; since e_{ti} is white noise with finite mean and constant variance.

APPLICATIONS

Penalty functions are widely used for model identification: Akaike Information Criterion (AIC), Bayesian Information Criterion (BIC) and Hannan-Quin Information Criterion (HQIC) are used as goodness-of fit for the model. The model with lowest criteria value is considered the best among the models for the simulated data, [9], [10]

$$AIC = \log [(\hat{\sigma}_{p,q}^2) + \frac{(p+q)^2}{n}] \tag{7}$$

$$BIC = \log [(\hat{\sigma}_{p,q}^2) + \frac{(p+q)\log(n)}{n}] \tag{8}$$

$$HQIC = \log [(\hat{\sigma}_{p,q}^2) + \frac{(p+q)2\log(\log(n))}{n}] \tag{9}$$

This approach has received tremendous application in the time series modeling in selecting the optimal model based on the principle of parsimony i.e keep it simple [11], [12], [13], [14], [15].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

From each iteration simulated, the values of the criteria for the assessment (AIC and BIC) were computed and their average values were recorded according to sample sizes as shown in Table 1 and 2. The values from the tables were plotted in Figures 1, 2, 3 and 4 respectively. The model with lowest criteria value is considered as the best

Table 1: AIC and BIC of GARCH Model for Non-Stationary Data from Normal distribution

Sample Sizes	AIC			BIC				
	GARCH (1,1)	GARCH (1,2)	GARCH (2,1)	GARCH (2,2)	GARCH (1,1)	GARCH (1,2)	GARCH (2,1)	GARCH (2,2)
20	11.2096	11.4756	11.4609	11.5399	11.40881	11.72458	11.7098	11.83863
40	10.7331	10.9793	10.9782	10.9520	10.90205	11.19049	11.1893	11.20538
60	10.3115	10.3719	10.2738	10.0463	10.45121	10.54647	10.4483	10.25582
80	9.47669	9.31042	10.0126	9.37806	9.595794	9.459299	10.1615	9.556716
100	8.78182	8.68118	8.80093	9.22339	8.886028	8.811442	8.93119	9.379708
120	8.02816	8.30220	8.65288	8.22628	8.121079	8.418349	8.76903	8.365662
140	7.74946	8.69473	7.80233	7.92102	7.833511	8.799798	7.90739	8.047094
160	7.45614	7.84134	7.92277	7.70299	7.533026	7.937441	8.01887	7.818316
180	7.48227	8.03085	7.66900	7.72761	7.553224	8.119546	7.75769	7.834051
200	7.66243	7.61109	7.76317	7.69116	7.728402	7.693553	7.84563	7.790109

From the table above, results of the performance of the four fitted models relatively, on a 1000 iterations simulated data at different sample sizes. The values of AIC and BIC on the average are recorded and tabulated as seen above and then their values plotted in Figures 1 and 2 respectively. It was observed that both the AIC and BIC values increases as the sample sizes increases of the simulated data. For the sample sizes 20, 40, 120, 140, 160 and 180 respectively; GARCH (1, 1) model was chosen as the best fit in the light of AIC and BIC. GARCH (1,2) model was the best fit at sample sizes 80, 100 and 200 respectively as having minimum of the criteria's. While at sample sizes 60; GARCH (2,2) model was the appropriate fit

Figure 1: Graph of the AIC values for GARCH (p, q) Models from a Non-normal Data

Figure 2: Graph of the BIC values for GARCH (p, q) Models from a Non- Normal Data

Table 2: HQIC and SBIC of GARCH Model for Non-Stationary Data from Normal distribution

Sample Sizes	HQIC				SBIC			
	GARCH(1,1)	GARCH(1,2)	GARCH(2,1)	GARCH(2,2)	GARCH(1,1)	GARCH(1,2)	GARCH(2,1)	GARCH(2,2)
20	11.24854	11.52424	11.50953	11.59822	11.14614	11.38111	11.36640	11.40991
40	10.79422	11.05571	11.05461	11.04365	10.71548	10.95252	10.95142	10.91442
60	10.36620	10.44021	10.34211	10.12830	10.30342	10.35942	10.26133	10.02870
80	9.524444	9.370111	10.07238	9.449691	9.472003	9.303205	10.00547	9.367826
100	8.823996	8.733901	8.853656	9.286660	8.778782	8.676493	8.796248	9.216727
120	8.065896	8.349371	8.700053	8.282888	8.026034	8.298913	8.649595	8.221598
140	7.783619	8.737432	7.845027	7.972254	7.747891	8.692304	7.799898	7.917547
160	7.487365	7.880365	7.961798	7.749824	7.454937	7.839467	7.920900	7.700317
180	7.511039	8.066814	7.704965	7.770773	7.481310	8.029364	7.667515	7.725491
200	7.689131	7.644464	7.796545	7.731203	7.661656	7.609885	7.761966	7.689429

Similarly, Table 2 presents results of the performance of the four fitted models relatively, on a 1000 iterations simulated data at different sample sizes. The values of HQIC and SIC on the average are recorded and tabulated as seen above and then their values plotted in Figures 3 and 4 respectively. It was observed that both the HQIC and SIC values increases as sample sizes increases of the simulated data. For the sample sizes 20, 40, 120, 140, 160 and 180 respectively; GARCH (1, 1) model was chosen as the best fit in the light of HQIC and SIC. GARCH (1,2) model was the best fit at sample sizes 80, 100 and 200 respectively. While at sample sizes 60 GARCH (2,2) was the best fit.

Figure 3: Graph of the HQIC values for GARCH (p, q) Models from a Non-Normal Data

Figure 4: Graph of the SIC values for GARCH (p, q) Models from a Non- Normal Data

Determination of Best order of ARMA Based on AIC, BIC, HQIC and FPE Criteria

From each of iteration simulated, the values of the criteria for the assessment (AIC, BIC, HQIC and SIC) were computed and their average values were recorded according to sample sizes as shown in Table 3 and 4. The values from the tables were plotted in figures 5, 6, 7 and 8 respectively. The model with lowest criteria value is considered as the best.

Table 3: AIC and BIC Values of GARCH Model for Non-Stationary Data from Exponential Distribution

Sample Sizes	AIC				BIC			
	GARCH (1,1)	GARCH (1,2)	GARCH (2,1)	GARCH (2,2)	GARCH (1,1)	GARCH (1,2)	GARCH (2,1)	GARCH (2,2)
20	11.1111	11.3923	12.2796	11.0511	11.31034	11.64130	12.5285	11.34983
40	11.3295	11.4182	10.9243	11.9098	11.49839	11.62936	11.1354	12.16315
60	10.6806	11.4754	11.7301	11.4099	10.82030	11.64995	11.9046	11.61942
80	11.2910	11.2158	10.9667	11.1516	11.41011	11.36469	11.1156	11.33033
100	11.5647	11.1337	10.9957	11.0940	11.66899	11.26402	11.1260	11.25033
120	10.8283	11.8678	11.0484	11.1437	10.92127	11.98395	10.9910	11.28311
140	10.8012	11.5286	11.0136	10.8220	10.88528	11.63367	11.1187	10.94815
160	10.5033	10.5136	11.1289	11.7099	10.58020	10.60977	11.2250	11.82528
180	11.0496	10.8466	11.3956	11.1439	11.12062	10.93530	11.4843	11.25036
200	11.1266	10.3756	11.2886	10.6036	11.19263	10.45810	11.3711	10.60364

Table 3 above presents results of the performance of the four fitted models relatively, on a 1000 iterations simulated data at different sample sizes. The values of AIC and BIC on the average are recorded and tabulated as seen above and then their values plotted in figures 5 and 6 respectively. It was seen that both the AIC and BIC values increases as the sample sizes increases of the simulated data. At sample sizes 20 GARCH (2, 2) was the best fit. At 40, 80 and 100

GARCH (2, 1) was the best fit. At sample sizes 60,120, 140 and 160 GARCH (1, 1) was chosen as the best fit. GARCH (1, 2) was the best fit at sample sizes 180 and 200 respectively.

Figure 5: Graph of the AIC values for GARCH (p, q) Models from a Non- Normal Data

Figure 6: Graph of the BIC values for GARCH (p, q) Models from a Non- Normal Data

Table 4: AIC and BIC Values of GARCH Model for Non-Stationary Data from Exponential Distribution

Sample Sizes	HQIC				SIC			
	GARCH(1,1)	GARCH(1,2)	GARCH(2,1)	GARCH(2,2)	GARCH(1,1)	GARCH(1,2)	GARCH(2,1)	GARCH(2,2)
20	11.15006	11.44096	12.32820	11.10943	11.04766	11.29783	12.18507	10.92112
40	11.39057	11.49458	11.00064	12.00142	11.31183	11.39139	10.89746	11.87218
60	10.73529	11.54369	11.79837	11.49191	10.67251	11.46291	11.71758	11.39231
80	11.33876	11.27550	11.02644	11.22330	11.28632	11.20859	10.95953	11.14144
100	11.60696	11.18648	11.15869	11.15729	11.56175	11.12907	11.27484	11.08735

120	10.86609	11.98395	11.20586	11.20034	10.82623	11.86451	11.15540	11.13905
140	10.83539	11.57131	11.05637	10.87331	10.79966	11.52618	11.01124	10.81860
160	10.53454	10.55269	11.16795	11.75679	10.50211	10.51180	11.12706	11.70728
180	11.07844	10.88257	11.43163	11.18708	11.04871	10.84512	11.39418	11.14180
200	11.15336	10.45810	11.32206	10.64368	11.12588	10.37444	11.32206	10.60190

Similarly, Table 4 above presents results of the performance of the four fitted models relatively, on a 1000 iterations simulated data at different sample sizes. The values of HQIC and SIC on the average are recorded and tabulated as seen above and then their values plotted in figures 7 and 8 respectively. It was revealed that both the HQIC and SIC values of increases as the sample sizes increases for the simulated data. for sample size 20 GARCH (2, 2) model was the best fit and for 40, 80 and 100 respectively; GARCH (2, 1) model was the best fit. For the sample sizes 60,120, 140 and 160 respectively; GARCH (1, 1) model was chosen as the best fit as having minimum of HQIC and SIC. GARCH (1, 2) was the best fit at sample sizes 180 and 200 respectively.

Figure 7: HQIC values for GARCH (p, q) Models from a Non- Normal Data

Figure 8: SIC values for GARCH (p, q) Models from a Non- Normal Data

Table 5: Forecasting performances of the Fitted Models on the Basis of AIC, BIC and MSE for a GARCH (1, 2) for Exponential Distribution

H	Sample size 20				Sample size 60				AIC	BIC	SIC	HQIC
	AIC	BIC	SIC	HQIC	AIC	BIC	SIC	HQIC				
5	7.90	8.15	7.81	7.95	7.96	8.13	7.95	8.03	7.64	7.72	7.64	7.67
10	8.44	8.69	8.35	8.49	8.26	8.43	8.25	8.25	7.61	7.69	7.61	7.64
15	7.76	7.85	7.76	7.80	7.92	8.10	7.91	7.99	7.76	7.85	7.76	7.80
20	9.38	9.56	9.37	9.45	8.27	8.44	8.26	8.34	9.38	9.56	9.37	9.45
25	7.66	7.73	7.66	7.66	7.76	7.93	7.74	7.82	8.15	8.23	8.15	8.18
30	7.61	7.69	7.61	7.64	7.66	7.73	7.66	7.69	7.66	7.73	7.66	7.69
35	7.69	7.94	7.60	7.74	7.61	7.69	7.61	7.64	7.61	7.61	7.64	7.65
40	8.06	8.31	7.96	8.11	7.76	7.85	7.76	7.80	7.76	7.85	7.76	7.80
45	7.72	7.97	7.63	7.77	9.38	9.56	9.37	9.45	7.54	7.62	7.54	7.57
50	7.95	8.20	7.85	7.99	7.96	8.14	7.95	8.03	7.60	7.61	7.62	7.64

The table above presents the results of the model fitted on non-stationary real life data. The sample sizes 48. Four models considered are ARMA (1, 1, 1), ARMA (1, 1, 2), ARMA (2, 1, 1) and ARMA (2, 1, 2) and the data used was temperature. ADF test of Stationarity was performed on the data and it was revealed that the data is stationary at levels. AIC, BIC and MSE are the criteria used in selecting the best fit among the four models. **ARMA (2,1, 2) model** is the best fit for the data, having the minimum of the three criteria's.

Table 6: Non- Stationary Normal GARCH

Sample Size	At Levels	GARCH (1,1)			GARCH (1,2)			GARCH (2,1)			GARCH (2,2)		
	ADF Test	AIC	BIC	HQIC	AIC	BIC	HQIC	AIC	BIC	HQIC	AIC	BIC	HQIC
27	-2.722 (0.297)	2.180	2.372	2.237	2.25	2.494	2.32548	2.2541	2.4941	2.32548	2.3282	2.6160	2.61610

Similarly, the table above presents the results of the model fitted on non-stationary real life data. The sample sizes 48. Four models considered are GARCH (1, 1), GARCH (1, 2), GARCH (2, 1) and GARCH (2, 2) and the data used was temperature. ADF test of Stationarity was performed on the data and it was revealed that the data is stationary at levels. AIC, BIC and HQIC are the criteria used in selecting the best fit among the four models. **GARCH (1, 1) model** is the best fit for the data, having the minimum of the three criteria.

CONCLUSION

The study concludes that the selections of the order for the models considered are tied more to the underlying distribution of the series in relation to the Stationarity and Non-Stationarity as it will lead to identification of proper model. Since the selection varies with the variation in the distribution of the series for the Generalized Autoregressive Conditional Heteroskedasticity (GARCH); the order selection is sensitive to the underlying distribution (i.e being normal of non-normal) of the series for larger sample sizes.

Reference to the analysis, results, discussions, findings and conclusion presented and reached in the preceding sections above. The following are thus recommended: That for every time series model order selection tests for normality and otherwise should be of priority just as that of Stationarity. That it is not always feasible to make a series stationary before modeling as great benefit can be drive form modeling a non-stationary data.

REFERENCES

1. Engle RF. Autoregressive Conditional Heteroscedasticity with Estimates of the Variance of United Kingdom Innovations, *Econometrica*, 1982:50, 987-1007
2. Baillie RT, & Bollerslev T, Common Stochastic Trends in a System of Exchange Rates, *Journal of Monetary Economics*, 1989:44, 167 – 181.
3. Teräsvirta T, An Introduction To Univariate GARCH Models, SSE/EFI Working Paper Series in Economics and Finance 646, Stockholm School of Economics. 2006.
4. Bollerslev T. Generalized Autoregressive Conditional Heteroskedasticity, *J. Econometrics*, 1986:31, 307-327.
5. Taylor SJ. *Modelling Financial Time Series*. John Wiley and Sons, Ltd., Chichester, 1986.
6. Barnett V, & Lewis T. *Outliers in Statistical Data*. Third Edition, John Wiley & Sons, New York. 1994.
7. Baillie RT & Bollerslev T, Common Stochastic Trends in a System of Exchange Rates, *Journal of Monetary Economics*, 1989:44, 167 – 181.
8. Li C. On Estimation of GARCH Models with an Application to Nordea Stock Prices. Department of Mathematics Uppsala University *U.U.D.M. Project Report*, 2007.
9. Akaike H. A New Look at the Statistical Model Identification. *IEEE Transactions on Automatic Control*, 1974:AC- 19, 716-723.
10. Schwarz G. Noop. *The Annals of Statistics* 1978:6, 461–464
11. Chen S. On Order Identification of Time Series Models and Its Applications; *A dissertation submitted to the Graduate School of New Brunswick Rutgers, The State University of New Jersey in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree of Doctor of Philosophy Graduate Program in Statistics and Biostatistic*, 2011.
12. Dibal NP, Imam A, & Abubakar MB. On Order and Regime Determination of SETAR Model in Modelling Nonlinear Stationary Time Series Data Structure: Application to Lafia Rainfall Data, Nasarawa State, Nigeria. *American Journal of Theoretical and Applied Statistics*, 2021:10(2): 89-98.
13. Akeyede I, Yahya WB, & Adeleke BL. On Forecast Strength of Some Linear and Nonlinear Time Series Models for Stationary Data Structure. *American Journal of Mathematics and Statistics*, 2015:5(4):163-177.
14. Van Dijk D, Teräsvirta T, & Franses P. Smooth Transition Autoregressive models – A Survey of Recent Developments. *Econometric Reviews*, 2002:21(1), 1–47.
15. Ang A, & Bekaert G. International Asset Allocation With Regime Shifts. *The Review of Financial Studies*, 2002: 15(4), 1137–118.